

Generation and Use of Cyclopropenyllithium Under Continuous Flow Conditions

Supplementary Information

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General Information

Solvents, Reagents & Reactions

Chemical symbols have their conventional meaning. SI units and their respective standard symbols have been used. Solvent removal was achieved using a Büchi R-300 rotary evaporator under reduced pressure (0 – 1000 mbar) with a bath temperature of 35 °C. Reactions were performed in cooled oven-dried glassware (90 °C for 12 hrs) under a nitrogen atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. Reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial suppliers and used as received, unless otherwise stated. *n*-Butyllithium solution (2.5 M in hexane) was purchased from Merck and titrated before use. *n*-Hexane was distilled from calcium chloride before use.

Chromatography

Flash column chromatography was performed using silica gel (40 – 63 µm, Geduran, Merck) using head pressure achieved by the use of head bellows. All solvents used for chromatography were obtained from commercial suppliers and used without further processing. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on aluminium-backed 0.25 mm precoated silica plates with fluorescent indicator (60 F254 Merck), and visualized under UV-light.

Analysis, Spectroscopy and Spectrometry of compounds

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker Ascend-400 (400 MHz for ¹H-NMR, 101 MHz for ¹³C{¹H}-NMR and 377 MHz for ¹⁹F-NMR). The measurements were conducted at ambient temperature, unless otherwise noted, and referenced to peak of the non-deuterated residual solvent. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm, δ) and to two decimal places for proton and fluorine shifts, and one decimal place for carbon shifts. Multiplicity of spectral peaks is assigned as follows: singlet (s), doublet (d), triplet (t), quartet (q), pentet (p) or multiplet (m), and combinations thereof. Spin-spin coupling constants (J) are reported to the nearest 0.1 Hz. ¹H NMR on the reaction crude was used to establish the diastereomeric ratio.

Thermo Scientific Nicolet Summit PRO FTIR Spectrometer was employed to obtain the infrared spectra. Samples were loaded neat and absorption frequencies are recorded in cm⁻¹.

Agilent S3 6530 accurate mass Q-TOF instrument and Excalibur data system were used to record the high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) spectra.

Flow Set-Up

Stainless steel (SUS304) T- mixers with inner diameter of 0.5 mm were manufactured by Sanko Seiki Co., Inc. Stainless steel (SUS316) tubing with inner diameter of 1 mm were purchased from GL Sciences and were cut into the appropriate lengths. Two stainless steel T-mixers (M1 and M2) and two stainless steel microtube reactors (R1 and R2) were employed for the lithiation of the tribromocyclopropyl derivatives (M1 inner diameter = 0.5 mm, R1 inner diameter ϕ = 1 mm, length L = 1000 mm) and for the quenching step (M2 inner diameter = 0.5 mm, R2 inner diameter ϕ =1 mm, length L = 1500 mm). Three precooling units (P1, P2 (inner diameter ϕ = 1 mm, length L = 1000 mm) and P3 (inner diameter ϕ = 1 mm, length L = 250 mm) were used.

Figure 1. Set up of the flow experiments

Optimization of Flow Synthesis of Cyclopropene derivatives

Entry	T [°C]	t ^{R1} [s]	L ₁ [cm]	t ^{R2} [s]	L ₂ [cm]	Conc. Ph ₂ C=O [M]	Ph ₂ C=O equiv.	Yield % ^a
1	0	15	50	30	150	0.145	1	57
2	0	15	50	30	150	0.217	1.5	50
3	0	15	50	30	150	0.101	0.7	52
4	0	10	40	30	150	0.145	1	37
5	0	7.5	25	30	150	0.145	1	33
6	0	30	100	30	150	0.145	1	80
7	0	60	200	30	150	0.145	1	52
8	0	15	50	40	200	0.145	1	54
9	-20	15	50	30	150	0.145	1	65
10	25	15	50	30	150	0.145	1	0 ^b

^aNMR yields were calculated using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as internal standard. ^bClogging observed.

Electrophiles collection

Compounds **A – M, P – T** are commercially available.

Compounds **N,O** and **S** were prepared according to procedures reported in literature. For the synthesis see the **Synthesis and characterization of compounds** section.

General Procedures

General procedure 1 (GP1) for the synthesis of starting materials Tribromocyclopropanes

The dibromocarbene addition was performed adapting a previously reported procedure.¹ To a vigorously stirred solution of bromoalkene (1 equiv), benzyltriethylammonium chloride (0.05 equiv) and bromoform (4.4 equiv), an aqueous 20 M NaOH solution (0.4 mL per mmol of bromoalkene) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at 25 °C until disappearance of the bromoalkene or no more progress was observed (TLC analysis). The crude was then extracted with DCM, the combined organic phases were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by column chromatography to afford the desired tribromocyclopropane.

Preparation of 0.42 M *n*-butyllithium solution (in hexane)

To *n*-hexane (16.5 mL, freshly distilled from calcium chloride) cooled to 0 °C was added dropwise commercial *n*-butyllithium solution (3.5 mL, 2.4 M in hexane). The resulting solution was used immediately.

General procedure 2 (GP2) for the synthesis of Cyclopropene derivatives in flow

The reactor was completely immersed into an ice bath (0°C). A solution of the tribromocyclopropane (0.114 M in THF) (flow rate: 1 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump) and a freshly prepared solution of n-butyllithium (0.42 M in n-hexane) (flow rate: 0.57 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump), were introduced to M1 (inner diameter = 0.5 mm) by syringe pumps. The resulting solution was passed through R1 [$\phi_1 = 1$ mm, $L_1 = 100$ cm ($t^{R1} = 30$ s)] and mixed in M2 (inner diameter = 0.5 mm) with a solution of electrophile (0.145 M in THF) (flow rate: 0.786 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump). The resulting solution was passed through R2 ($\phi_2 = 1.0$ mm, $L_2 = 150$ cm ($t^{R2} = 30$ s)). After reaching the steady state (collection for one minute), the solution was collected for 5 minutes in a separate vial containing an excess of water as the quench. The reaction mixture was extracted with Et₂O (3 x 5 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified as described per example to yield the desired products.

General procedure 3 (GP3) as a representative example of a detailed synthetic method at 2.4 mmol scale

The reactor was completely immersed into an ice bath ($0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). A solution of (1,2,2-Tribromocyclopropyl)benzene (1.212 g, 3.42 mmol) in THF (30 mL, 0.114 M) (flow rate: 1 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump) and a freshly prepared solution of *n*-butyllithium (30 mL, 0.42 M in *n*-hexane) (flow rate: 0.57 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump), were introduced to M_1 (inner diameter = 0.5 mm) by syringe pumps. The resulting solution was passed through R_1 [$\phi_1 = 1\text{ mm}$, $L_1 = 100\text{ cm}$ ($t_{R1} = 30\text{ s}$)] and mixed in M_2 (inner diameter = 0.5 mm) with a solution of benzophenone (0.792 g, 4.35 mmol) in THF (30 mL, 0.145 M) (flow rate: 0.786 mL/min by Harvard Apparatus PHD ULTRA syringe pump). The resulting solution was passed through R_2 ($\phi_2 = 1.0\text{ mm}$, $L_2 = 200\text{ cm}$ ($t_{R2} = 30\text{ s}$)). After reaching the steady state (collection for one minute), the solution was collected for twenty one minutes in a separate round bottom flask containing an excess of water as the quench. The reaction mixture was extracted with Et_2O (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na_2SO_4 and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The desired product was obtained as a yellow oil (0.569 g, 1.91 mmol, 80%) and was purified by flash column chromatography.

Assessing performance with metrics

To evaluate the efficiency of the developed methodology it has been compared to the previously reported batch protocol on the basis of three different factors: overall process time, productivity, and space time yield. To do so we selected entries **2a**, **2h**, **2r**, **2s** and **2z** and compared the reactions according to both protocols and considering the same scale (10 mmol).

Process time

Process times for the batch protocol are obtained considering literature reported data for 10 mmol of starting material processed, and take into consideration warm-cool sequences. Flow process times are obtained considering the time needed to obtain the desired amount of product. The gathered numerical data are expressed in Figure 2 and the values reported in Table 1.

Figure 2. Process Times of the selected entries

	2a	2h	2r	2s	2z
Batch Process Time ^{1,2,3} (h)	3	3	3	3	3
Flow Process Time (h)	1.29	1.39	1.42	1.31	2.22

Table 1.

Productivity

$$\text{Productivity} = \frac{\text{Mass of desired product (g)}}{\text{Process time (h)}}$$

Productivity was calculated using the given mathematical formula. The gathered numerical data are expressed in Figure 3 and the values reported in Table 2.

Figure 3. Productivity of the selected entries

	2a	2h	2r	2s	2z
Desired amount of product (g)	2.10	1.32	1.05	0.96	1.29
Batch Productivity^{1,2,3} (g/h)	0.7	0.44	0.35	0.32	0.43
Mmol processed in flow (mmol/min)	0.114	0.114	0.114	0.114	0.114
Flow Yield %	80	80	77	70	45
Flow Productivity (g/h)	1.63	0.95	0.74	0.73	0.58

Table 2.

Space Time Yield STY

$$\text{Space Time Yield} = \frac{\text{Mass of desired product in 1 Residence Time (g)}}{\text{Residence Time (h)} * \text{Reactor Volume (L)}}$$

Space Time Yields were calculated using the given mathematical formula. For batch procedures the value of the residence time was assumed to be equal to the reaction time and the volume of the reactor was assumed to be equal to the volume of the solvent used. The gathered numerical data are expressed in Figure 4 and the values reported in Table 3.

Figure 4. Space Time Yield of the selected entries

	2a	2h	2r	2s	2z
Mass of product per Residence Time in Flow (g)	0.027	0.016	0.012	0.012	0.01
Mass of product per Residence Time in Batch^{1,2,3} (g)	1.49	0.92	0.33	0.48	1.29
Volume of the reactor (flow) (L)	$1.96 \cdot 10^{-3}$				
Volume of the reactor (batch)^{1,2,3} (L)	0.1	0.1	0.048	0.03	0.1
Residence Time (flow) (h)	$16.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$				
Residence Time (batch)^{1,2,3} (h)	3	3	3	3	3
Batch STY^{1,2,3} (g/Lh)	4.97	3.07	7.33	21.38	4.3
Flow STY (g/Lh)	832.69	486.75	376.21	371.94	293.88

Table 3

Synthesis and characterization of compounds

(1,2,2-Tribromocyclopropyl)benzene, 1a

Prepared following GP1 using *(1-bromovinyl)benzene* (5.1 g, 28.0 mmol). After flash column chromatography (hexane), the title compound was obtained as a white solid (8.5 g, 24 mmol, 86%).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.51 – 7.45 (2H, m), 7.42 – 7.31 (3H, m), 2.51 (1H, d, $J = 9.3$ Hz), 2.25 (1H, d, $J = 9.3$ Hz)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*¹

1-Methyl-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene, 1b

Prepared following GP1 using *1-(1-bromovinyl)-4-methylbenzene* (1.44 g, 7.28 mmol). After flash column chromatography (hexane), the title compound was obtained as a white solid (1.4 g, 3.8 mmol, 52%).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.51 – 7.45 (2H, m), 7.42 – 7.31 (3H, m), 2.49 (d, $J = 9.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.36 (3H, s), 2.25 (d, $J = 9.3$ Hz, 1H).

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*⁴

1-Chloro-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene, 1c

Prepared following GP1 using 1-(1-bromovinyl)-4-chlorobenzene (9.9 g, 45.7 mmol). After flash column chromatography (hexane), the title compound was obtained as a white solid (9.7 g, 25.0 mmol, 55%).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.43 – 7.39 (2H, m), 7.36 (2H, d, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 2.47 (1H, d, $J = 9.4$ Hz), 2.25 (1H, d, $J = 9.4$ Hz).

The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported. ⁴

1-Fluoro-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene, 1d

Prepared following GP1 using 1-(1-bromovinyl)-4-fluorobenzene (8.8 g, 43.8 mmol). After flash column chromatography (hexane), the title compound was obtained as a white solid (4.7 g, 12.5 mmol, 29%).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.43 – 7.39 (2H, m), 7.36 (2H, d, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 2.47 (1H, d, $J = 9.4$ Hz), 2.25 (1H, d, $J = 9.4$ Hz)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -111.55 (tt, $J = 8.7, 5.1$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 162.8 (d, $J = 249.6$ Hz), 136.3 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz), 131.2 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz), 115.9 (d, $J = 22.1$ Hz), 42.2, 37.5, 31.8

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 2925, 2853, 1602, 1509, 1415, 1233, 1054, 993

HRMS: no ionization observed in ESI+ or ESI- mode

1,1,2-Tribromo-2-methylcyclopropane, **1e**

Prepared following GP1 using *2-bromo-3-methylbut-2-ene* (1.54 g, 10.34 mmol). After flash column chromatography (hexane), the title compound was obtained as a white solid (2.51 g, 7.82 mmol, 76%).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 2.01 (3H, s), 1.52 (3H, s), 1.37 (3H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*¹

N-(Diphenylmethylene)-2-methylpropane-2-sulfonamide, **N**

Compound **N** was prepared according to a previously reported procedure.⁵

Benzophenone (0.91 g, 5 mmol), *2-methylpropane-2-sulfonamide* (0.68 g, 5 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *triethylamine* (1.01g, 10 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) were dissolved in 20 mL of *dichloroethane*, and stirred. TiCl_4 (0.47 g, 2.5 mmol, 0.5 equiv.) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was heated at reflux for 3-5 h. The mixture was filtered through Celite and washed with dichloromethane. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the residue purified by flash silica column chromatography (hexane to 5:1 hexane:ethyl acetate) to afford the desired product (0.60 g, 2 mmol, 40%) as a white solid.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.80 – 7.35 (10H, m), 1.56 (9H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*⁶

2,2,2-Trifluoro-*N*,1-diphenylethan-1-imine, **O**

Compound **O** was prepared adapting a previously reported procedure.⁵

2,2,2-Trifluoroacetophenone (0.87 g, 5 mmol), *aniline* (0.46 g, 5 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (1.68 g, 15 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) were dissolved in 50 mL of *chlorobenzene*, and stirred. $TiCl_4$ (0.47 g, 2.5 mmol, 0.5 equiv.) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was heated at reflux overnight. The mixture was filtered through Celite and washed with dichloromethane. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the product obtained without further purification (1.1 g, 4.25 mmol, 85%) as a yellow oil.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.38 – 7.27 (4H, m), 7.24 – 7.16 (4H, m), 7.07 – 7.01 (2H, m), 6.77 – 6.72 (2H, m).

¹⁹F-NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_F -70.01 (tt, $J = 8.7, 5.1$ Hz)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*⁷

N*-(Diphenylmethylene)-4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)benzenesulfonamide, **S*

Compound **S** was prepared according to a previously reported procedure.⁵

Benzophenone (1.82 g, 10 mmol), *Celecoxib* (1.36 g, 10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *triethylamine* (2.02 g, 20 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) were dissolved in 40 mL of *dichloroethane*, and stirred. $TiCl_4$ (0.94 g, 5 mmol, 0.5 equiv.) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was heated at reflux for 5 h. The mixture was filtered through Celite and washed with dichloromethane. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the residue purified by flash silica column chromatography (hexane to 5:1 hexane:ethyl acetate) to afford the desired product (0.76 g, 2 mmol, 20%) .

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ_H 7.99 – 7.90 (2H, m), 7.61 – 7.53 (6H, m), 7.49 – 7.39 (6H, m), 7.22 – 7.16 (2H, m), 7.15 – 7.10 (2H, m), 6.75 (1H, s), 2.38 (3H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*⁵

Diphenyl(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, **2a**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and *benzophenone*. Quantitative 1H -NMR yield of compound **2a** was found to be 80% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (136 mg, 0.456 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 95:5 hexane:DCM).

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ_H 7.52 – 7.46 (4H, m), 7.40 – 7.25 (11H, m), 2.82 (1H, s), 1.58 (2H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*¹

Diphenyl(2-(*p*-tolyl)cycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, 2b

Prepared following GP2 using *1-methyl-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene 1b* and *benzophenone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2b** was found to be 67% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (119 mg, 0.382 mmol). The title product was obtained as a pale yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.50 – 7.39 (4H, m), 7.38-7.32 (6H, m), 7.18 – 7.12 (4H, m), 2.84 (1H, s), 2.36 (3H, s), 1.56 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 144.8, 138.8, 130.2, 129.3, 128.5, 127.7, 126.8, 125.9, 116.1, 111.3, 78.2, 21.5, 9.6

IR (neat, v cm^{-1}): 3445, 3025, 2952, 2866, 1840, 1655, 1599, 1490, 1446, 1319, 1164, 1018, 900

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{ONa}$ 335.1412; Found 335.1407

(2-(4-Chlorophenyl)cycloprop-1-en-1-yl)diphenylmethanol, 2c

Prepared following GP2 using *1-chloro-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene 1c* and *benzophenone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2c** was found to be 45% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (86 mg, 0.257 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 95:5 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.47 - 7.42 (4H, m), 7.39 - 7.58 (8H, m), 7.18 - 7.13 (2H, m), 2.78 (1H, s), 1.56 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 144.6, 134.6, 131.4, 128.9, 128.6, 127.9, 127.3, 126.8, 118.4, 110.5, 78.3, 10.0

IR (neat, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3445, 3021, 2952, 1840, 1655, 1599, 1490, 1446, 1133, 927

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClONa}$ 332.0968; Found 355.0862

(2-(4-Fluorophenyl)cycloprop-1-en-1-yl)diphenylmethanol, 2d

Prepared following GP2 using *1-fluoro-4-(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene 1d* and *benzophenone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2d** was found to be 72% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (130 mg, 0.410 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 95:5 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.49-7.43 (4H, m), 7.39-7.28 (6H, m), 7.23-7.18 (2H, m), 7.02-6.95 (2H, m), 2.83 (1H, s), 1.57 (2H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -111.94 (tt, $J = 8.7, 5.5$ Hz).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 162.9 (d, $J = 249.4$ Hz), 144.7, 132.1 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 128.5, 127.9, 126.8, 125.1 (d, $J = 3.3$ Hz), 116.9 (d, $J = 3.0$ Hz), 115.7 (d, $J = 21.9$ Hz), 110.5, 78.2, 9.9

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3447, 3060, 2924, 2869, 1654, 1599, 1505, 1448, 1222, 1153, 1020

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{FONa}$ 339.1161; Found 339.1151

(2-Phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)di-*p*-tolylmethanol, 2e

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and di-*p*-tolylmethanone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2e** was found to be 68% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (126 mg, 0.387 mmol). The title product was obtained as a pale yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.47 – 7.30 (9H, m), 7.25 – 7.18 (4H, m), 2.86 (1H, s), 2.42 (6H, s), 1.61 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 141.9, 137.3, 130.3, 129.1, 128.9, 128.5, 128.5, 126.7, 118.0, 110.8, 78.1, 21.2, 9.8

IR (neat, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3447, 2949, 2867, 1509, 1161, 1019, 809, 758, 691

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{ONa}$ 349.1568; Found 349.1582

Bis(4-fluorophenyl)(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, 2f

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and bis(4-fluorophenyl)methanone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2f** was found to be 71% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (135 mg, 0.405 mmol). The title product was obtained as a pale yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.50 – 7.43 (4H, m), 7.41 – 7.30 (5H, m), 7.12 – 7.04 (4H, m), 3.01 (1H, s), 1.60 (2H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -114.40 (ddd, $J = 8.4, 5.3, 3.1$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 162.4 (d, $J = 246.8$ Hz), 140.3 (d, $J = 3.2$ Hz), 130.3, 128.9, 128.7, 128.6 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz), 128.4, 117.0, 115.3 (d, $J = 21.4$ Hz), 111.6, 77.4, 9.7

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3437, 3060, 2872, 1599, 1504, 1223, 1156, 906, 892, 729, 692

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{F}_2\text{ONa}$ 357.1067; Found 357.1066

Bis(4-chlorophenyl)(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, **2g**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and bis(4-chlorophenyl)methanone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2g** was found to be 62% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (130 mg, 0.353 mmol). The title product was obtained as a viscous pale yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 20:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.42 – 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.39 – 7.37 (m, 3H), 7.36 – 7.28 (m, 8H), 2.82 (s, 1H), 1.54 (s, 2H)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 142.8, 133.9, 130.3, 129.0, 128.7, 128.7, 128.3, 128.2, 116.4, 112.1, 77.5, 9.7

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3438, 1674, 1590, 1487, 1399, 1090, 1013, 914, 814, 758, 691

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}^{35}\text{Cl}_2\text{ONa}$ 389.0476; Found 389.0473

2-(2-Phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)propan-2-ol, **2h**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and acetone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2h** was found to be 80% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (79 mg, 0.456 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 20:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.60 – 7.53 (2H, m), 7.43 – 7.37 (2H, m), 7.34 – 7.27 (1H, m), 1.61 (6H, s), 1.34 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 129.9, 129.4, 128.7, 128.3, 118.8, 108.6, 69.7, 28.7, 7.5

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3388, 2973, 2868, 1363, 1160, 1019, 760, 692

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONa}$ 197.0942; Found 197.0932

1-(2-Phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)cyclobutan-1-ol, **2i**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and cyclobutanone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2i** was found to be 80% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (85 mg, 0.456 mmol). The title product was obtained as a colourless oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 5:1 hexane:Et₂O).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} 7.62 – 7.56 (2H, m), 7.44 – 7.38 (2H, m), 7.34 – 7.29 (1H, m), 2.54 – 2.47 (2H, m), 2.45 – 2.37 (2H, m), 2.28 (1H, br s), 1.96 – 1.82 (2H, m), 1.43 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} 129.8, 129.4, 128.7, 128.3, 116.7, 109.0, 73.3, 36.5, 13.0, 7.7

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3357, 2945, 2867, 1744, 1491, 1245, 1018, 758, 691

HRMS (ESI-) m/z : [M - H]⁻ Calcd for C₁₃H₁₃O 185.0972; Found 185.0981

1-(2-Phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)cyclohexan-1-ol, **2j**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and cyclohexanone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2j** was found to be 74% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (90 mg, 0.421 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 5:1 hexane:Et₂O).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} 7.62 – 7.56 (2H, m), 7.45 – 7.39 (2H, m), 7.35 – 7.28 (1H, m), 2.08 – 2.00 (2H, m), 1.97 (1H, br s), 1.85 – 1.73 (4H, m), 1.52 – 1.44 (4H, m), 1.32 (2H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} 129.9, 129.5, 128.6, 128.3, 118.1, 109.5, 70.8, 37.5, 25.5, 22.7, 6.6

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3363, 2930, 2860, 1744, 1445, 1258, 1016, 757, 690

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₅H₁₈ONa 237.1250; Found 237.1236

1-Phenyl-1-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethan-1-ol, **2k**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and acetophenone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2k** was found to be 68% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (92 mg, 388 μmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.57-7.45 (4H, m), 7.42-7.34 (4H, m), 7.34-7.28 (2H, m), 1.93 (3H, s), 1.44 (1H, d, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 1.40 (1H, d, $J = 7.4$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 145.5, 130.1, 129.1, 128.7, 128.6, 128.5, 127.6, 125.2, 118.0, 110.0, 73.5, 29.8, 8.3

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3441, 3058, 2922, 1679, 1598, 1491, 1068, 1027, 911, 761

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{ONa}$ 259.1099; Found 259.1108

2,2,2-Trifluoro-1-phenyl-1-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethan-1-ol, **2l**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and 2,2,2-trifluoro-1-phenylethan-1-one. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2l** was found to be 76% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (125 mg, 0.433 μmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 98:2 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.68 - 7.61 (2H, m), 7.61- 7.56 (2H, m), 7.47- 7.36 (6H, m), 2.96 (1H, s), 1.56 (1H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz), 1.51 (1H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -78.53 (s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 135.5, 130.6, 129.7, 129.4, 128.9, 128.6, 127.9, 127.0, 124.1 (q, $J = 287.1$ Hz), 115.4, 109.7, 76.5 (q, $J = 30.5$ Hz), 8.1

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3452, 3062, 2880, 1842, 1598, 1449, 1258, 1025, 760, 693

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{F}_3\text{ONa}$ 313.0816; Found 313.0831

4-Methyl-*N*-(phenyl(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methyl)benzenesulfonamide, **2m**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and *N*-benzylidene-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2m** was found to be 20% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (43 mg, 0.114 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 5:1 hexane:EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.68 – 7.63 (2H, m), 7.37 – 7.29 (7H, m), 7.25 – 7.21 (2H, m), 5.76 (1H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 5.21 (1H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz), 2.31 (3H, s), 1.24 (1H, d, $J = 7.3$ Hz), 1.01 (1H, d, $J = 7.3$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): 143.5, 138.2, 137.5, 129.9, 129.5, 129.0, 128.7, 128.5, 128.5, 128.3, 127.3, 127.3, 112.6, 111.6, 55.2, 21.5, 8.0

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3274, 3060, 2871, 1597, 1493, 1325, 1155, 812, 695

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_2\text{SNa}$ 398.1185; Found 398.1192

***N*-(2,2,2-Trifluoro-1-phenyl-1-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethyl)aniline, 2n**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and 2,2,2-trifluoro-*N*,1-diphenylethan-1-imine. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2n** was found to be 67% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (139 mg, 0.382 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 95:5 hexane:DCM).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.86 – 7.77 (2H, m), 7.51 – 7.46 (5H, m), 7.44 – 7.36 (3H, m), 7.02 (2H, dd, $J = 8.4, 7.5$ Hz), 6.71 (1H, t, $J = 6.7$ Hz), 6.56 – 6.50 (2H, m), 4.80 (1H, s), 1.51 (1H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz), 1.46 (1H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -75.66 (s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 143.7, 134.7, 130.6, 129.5, 129.3, 129.2, 128.9, 128.8, 128.7, 128.3, 125.2 (q, $J = 287.2$ Hz), 119.5, 116.8, 115.4, 109.7, 66.1 (q, $J = 27.2$ Hz), 9.3

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3408, 3058, 2875, 1602, 1497, 1247, 1164, 757, 690

HRMS (ESI-) m/z : $[M - H]^-$ - Calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{F}_3\text{N}$ 364.1319; Found 364.1313

Diphenyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, **2o**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *benzophenone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2o** was found to be 98% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (147 mg, 0.559 mmol). The title product was obtained as a colourless oil without further purification.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.47 - 7.43 (4H, m), 7.34-7.28 (4H, m), 7.27-7.23 (2H, m), 2.42 (1H, s) 2.02 (3H, s), 1.11 (6H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 145.6, 128.2, 127.3, 126.6, 124.1, 79.2, 25.8, 22.9, 8.7

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3472, 3050, 2911, 2853, 1846, 1684, 1491, 1158, 1012

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{ONa}$ 287.1406; Found 287.1412

Bis(4-fluorophenyl)(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, 2p

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *bis(4-fluorophenyl)methanone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2p** was found to be 69% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard. The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 98:2).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.43- 7.35 (4H, m), 7.04- 6.96 (4H, m), 2.42 (1H, s), 2.01 (3H, s), 1.10 (6H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -115.46 (ddd, $J = 8.6, 5.4, 3.2$ Hz).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 162.2 (d, $J = 246.1$ Hz), 141.3 (d, $J = 3.1$ Hz), 128.4 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 124.4, 115.0 (d, $J = 21.4$ Hz), 78.4, 25.7, 23.0, 8.7

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3463, 2932, 2856, 1846, 1601, 1364, 1224, 1156, 1014, 830

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{F}_2\text{ONa}$ 323.1224; Found 323.1232

Bis(4-chlorophenyl)(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, **2q**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *bis(4-chlorophenyl)methanone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2q** was found to be 67% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (127 mg, 0.3819 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 99:1).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.39 - 7.34 (4H, m), 7.32 - 7.27 (4H, m), 2.45 (1H, s), 2.02 (3H, s), 1.11 (6H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 143.8, 133.5, 128.4, 128.0, 127.6, 125.0, 78.4, 25.7, 23.1, 8.7

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3459, 2958, 2854, 1845, 1488, 1364, 1155, 1091, 1013, 896

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{Cl}_2\text{ONa}$ 355.0633; Found 355.0636

2-(2,3,3-Trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)propan-2-ol, **2r**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *acetone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2r** was found to be 77% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (62 mg, 0.439 mmol). The title product was obtained as a colourless oil without further purification.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 1.98 (3H, s), 1.68 (1H, br s), 1.41 (6H, s), 1.13 (6H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 128.7, 119.7, 71.0, 29.4, 25.9, 21.8, 8.5

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3368, 2956, 2926, 2854, 1979, 1442, 1362, 1167, 1046, 949, 805

HRMS (ESI-) m/z : $[\text{M} - \text{H}]^-$ Calcd for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{O}$ 139.1128; Found 139.1121

1-(2,3,3-Trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)cyclobutan-1-ol, **2s**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *cyclobutanone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2s** was found to be 70% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (61 mg, 0.398 mmol). The title product was obtained as a white amorphous solid without further purification.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 2.32 – 2.21 (4H, m), 2.07 (1H, s), 2.03 (3H, s), 1.77 – 1.65 (2H, m), 1.18 (6H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*²

1-Phenyl-1-(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethan-1-ol, **2t**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *acetophenone*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2t** was found to be 45% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (52 mg, 0.256 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 98:2).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.54 - 7.49 (2H, m), 7.37- 7.31 (2H, m), 7.28- 7.22 (1H, m), 2.03 (1H, s), 2.00 (3H, s), 1.71 (3H, s), 1.14 (3H, s), 1.14 (3H, s) (Two singlets overlapping)

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 146.6, 128.6, 128.2, 127.1, 125.1, 121.6, 74.7, 30.5, 26.0, 25.8, 22.4, 8.6

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3419, 2928, 1849, 1601, 1445, 1176, 1027, 760

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{ONa}$ 225.1256; Found 225.1262

2,2,2-Trifluoro-1-phenyl-1-(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethan-1-ol, **2u**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane* **1e** and *2,2,2-trifluoro-1-phenylethan-1-one*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2u** was found to be 65% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (95 mg, 0.371 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 98:2).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.63 - 7.57 (2H, m), 7.43 - 7.35 (3H, m), 2.55 (1H, s), 2.10 (3H, s), 1.21 (3H, s), 1.16 (3H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -79.51 (s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 136.1, 129.4, 128.9, 128.2, 127.0, 124.8 (q, $J = 286.2$) 122.3, 76.6 (q, $J = 30.5$), 25.8, 25.4, 8.9

IR (neat, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3610, 2919, 1850, 1450, 1265, 1047, 900, 759

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_3\text{ONa}$ 279.0973; Found 279.2501

Cyclopropyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanone, **2v**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane* **1e** and *N-methoxy-N-methylcyclopropanecarboxamide*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2v** was found to be 31% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (27 mg, 0.177 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 95:5).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 2.28 (3H, s), 2.10 (1H, ddt, $J = 9.1, 8.0, 4.6$ Hz), 1.24 (6H, s), 1.15 - 1.10 (2H, m), 0.99 - 0.93 (2H, m)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 195.0, 142.9, 123.7, 25.4, 24.5, 22.3, 11.2, 10.8

IR (neat, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$): 2924, 2858, 1809, 1652, 1431, 1378, 1213, 1102, 1030, 977

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONa}$ 173.0943; Found 173.0935

4-Methyl-*N*-(phenyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methyl)benzenesulfonamide, **2w**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *N-methoxy-N-methylcyclopropanecarboxamide*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2w** was found to be 15% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (29 mg, 0.086 mmol). The crude compound was washed with hexane and the title product was afforded after removing the solvent under reduced pressure.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.69- 7.63 (m, 2H), 7.24- 7.17 (m, 7H), 5.39 (dd, $J= 7.7, 1.5$ Hz, 1H), 5.04 (d, $J= 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 2.39 (s, 3H), 1.79 (d, $J= 1.5$ Hz, 3H), 0.96 (s, 3H), 0.84 (s, 3H)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 143.3, 139.4, 138.0, 129.6, 128.6, 127.8, 127.3, 127.1, 125.1, 123.0, 55.3, 25.5, 25.1, 22.2, 21.6, 8.4

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3269, 3030, 2854, 2154, 1857, 1455, 1160, 1093, 813

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_2\text{SNa}$ 364.1347; Found 364.1343

N*-(Diphenyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methyl)-2-methylpropane-2-sulfonamide, **2x*

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *N-(diphenylmethylene)-2-methylpropane-2-sulfonamide*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2x** was found to be 59% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (129 mg, 0.336 mmol). The title product was obtained as a white amorphous solid after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to hexane:EtOAc 10:1).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.50 – 7.44 (4H, m), 7.34 – 7.27 (5H, m), 7.26 – 7.24 (1H, m), 4.69 (1H, s), 2.06 (3H, s), 1.12 (9H, s), 0.95 (6H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 142.7, 129.2, 128.0, 127.7, 127.6, 123.6, 70.2, 60.7, 25.1, 24.1, 23.6, 8.8

IR (neat, v cm^{-1}): 2924, 2858, 1809, 1652, 1431, 1378, 1213, 1102, 1030, 977

HRMS (ESI-) m/z : $[\text{M} - \text{H}]^-$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{28}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ 382.1846; Found 382.1857

***N*-(2,2,2-Trifluoro-1-phenyl-1-(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)ethyl)aniline, 2y**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *2,2,2-trifluoro-N,1-diphenylethan-1-imine*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2y** was found to be 10% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (19 mg, 0.057 mmol). The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane:EtOAc 98:2).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.70 - 7.63 (2H, m), 7.43-7.35 (3H, m), 7.03 - 6.97 (2H, m), 6.73 - 6.67 (1H, m), 6.39 - 6.33 (2H, m), 4.43 (1H, s), 1.93 (3H, s), 1.02 (3H, s), 0.94 (3H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -77.42 (s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 144.4, 135.0, 129.3, 129.0, 128.9, 128.6, 125.2 (q, $J = 285.3$ Hz), 120.4, 119.1, 116.6, 66.5 (q, $J = 27.3$ Hz), 25.7, 24.8, 23.1, 9.0

IR (neat, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$): 3404, 2936, 2857, 1603, 1498, 1450, 1256, 911, 722

HRMS (ESI-) m/z : [M - H]- Calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{F}_3\text{N}$ 330.1470; Found 330.1476

Phenyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methanol, 2z

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *2,2,2-benzaldehyde*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2z** was found to be 45% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (48 mg, 0.256 mmol). The title product was obtained as a colourless oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to hexane:EtOAc 98:2).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.43 - 7.39 (2H, m), 7.32 - 7.38 (2H, m), 7.31 - 7.26 (1H, m), 5.67 (1H, s), 1.99 (3H, d, $J = 1.4$ Hz), 1.12 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, s)

*The spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported.*¹

(E)-3-Phenyl-1-(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)prop-2-en-1-ol, 2aa

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *trans-cinnamaldehyde*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **2aa** was found to be 60% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard. The title product was obtained as a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 95:5 hexane/ Et_2O).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.41 – 7.38 (2H, m), 7.34 – 7.30 (2H, m), 7.27 – 7.24 (1H, m), 6.65 (1H), 6.31 (1H, dd, $J = 15.9, 6.3$ Hz), 5.29 (1H, td, $J = 5.2, 1.3$ Hz), 2.05 (3H, d, $J = 1.4$ Hz), 1.80 (1H, d, $J = 5.2$ Hz), 1.17 (3H, s), 1.16 (3H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 136.9, 130.6, 129.6, 128.7, 127.9, 126.7, 124.0, 123.7, 69.5, 26.1, 21.8, 9.1

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3332, 2955, 2910, 2853, 1856, 1668, 1495, 1362, 1068, 961, 691

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{ONa}$ 237.1250; Found 237.1249

1,7,7-Trimethyl-2-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol, 3a

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and Camphor. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **3a** was found to be 44% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (67 mg, 0.251 mmol, d.r. > 95:5). The title product was obtained as a single diastereoisomer, affording a colourless oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:Et₂O).

Data reported for major diastereoisomer

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} 7.65 – 7.57 (2H, m), 7.44 – 7.38 (2H, m), 7.34 – 7.29 (1H, m), 2.35 – 2.28 (1H, m), 2.13 (1H, app. d, $J=13.2$ Hz), 1.99 (1H, br s), 1.89 (1H, t, $J=4.4$ Hz), 1.76 (1H, tdd, $J=12.3, 7.8, 4.4$ Hz), 1.49 – 1.39 (2H, m), 1.38 (2H, s), 1.28 – 1.23 (1H, m), 1.21 (3H, s), 1.06 (3H, s), 0.91(3H, s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} 129.8, 129.5, 128.7, 128.3, 119.0, 110.0, 81.0, 54.4, 49.3, 45.9, 45.7, 31.5, 27.4, 21.1, 20.9, 11.3, 9.6

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3566, 3478, 2951, 2867, 1836, 1737, 1597, 1062, 1019, 759

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₉H₂₄ONa 291.1719; Found 291.1742

2-Methyl-1-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)-5-(prop-1-en-2-yl)cyclohex-2-en-1-ol, 3b

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and (*R*)-(-)-Carvone. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **3b** was found to be 46% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (69 mg, 0.266 mmol, d.r. > 95:5). The title product was obtained as a single diastereoisomer, affording a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:Et₂O).

Data reported for major diastereoisomer

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} 7.58 – 7.54 (2H, m), 7.43 – 7.38 (2H, m), 7.33 (1H, dt, $J = 4.2, 1.7$ Hz), 5.69 – 5.65 (1H, m), 4.76 -4.72 (2H, m), 2.48 – 2.39 (1H, m), 2.33 (1H, dt, $J = 12.2, 2.1$ Hz), 2.21 – 2.15 (m, 1H), 2.09 – 2.02 (1H, m), 1.92 (1H, app. t), 1.83 (3H, dt, $J = 2.6, 1.3$ Hz), 1.72 (3H, s), 1.39 (2H, d, $J = 2.1$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} 148.7, 136.3, 130.0, 129.3, 128.7, 128.4, 124.9, 116.9, 110.5, 109.4, 73.7, 41.3, 39.8, 31.2, 20.7, 17.8, 7.8

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3408, 3079, 2964, 2867, 1644, 1445, 1374, 1019, 888, 758

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₉H₂₂ONa 289.1563; Found 289.1567

***N*-(Diphenyl(2,3,3-trimethylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methyl)-4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)benzenesulfonamide, 3c**

Prepared following GP2 using *1,1,2-tribromo-2,3,3-trimethylcyclopropane 1e* and *N-(diphenylmethylene)-4-(5-(*p*-tolyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)benzenesulfonamide*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **3c** was found to be 80% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (286 mg, 0.456 mmol). The title product was obtained as a white crystalline solid after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 5:1 hexane/EtOAc).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.26 – 7.22 (4H, m), 7.21 – 7.18 (7h, m), 7.17 – 7.13 (5H, m), 7.09 – 7.05 (2H, m), 6.72 (1H, s), 5.42 (1H, s), 2.37 (3H, s), 2.02 (3H, s), 0.96 (6H, s)

$^{19}\text{F-NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{F} -62.36 (s)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 145.2, 144.0 (q, $J = 38.5$ Hz), 141.8, 141.7, 140.9, 139.8, 129.8, 129.0, 128.9, 128.1, 127.8, 127.8, 127.7, 126.0, 124.8, 124.1, 121.3 (q, $J = 269.1$ Hz), 106.4, 69.0, 25.2, 23.8, 21.4, 8.6

IR (neat, ν cm^{-1}): 3228, 2927, 2856, 1849, 1470, 1323, 1137, 1093, 969, 805

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{32}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SNa}$ 650.2060; Found 650.2068

Melting point: 194.3 – 196.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

Isopropyl 2-(4-((4-chlorophenyl)(hydroxy)(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)methyl)phenoxy)-2-methylpropanoate, 3d

Prepared following GP2 using *(1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene 1a* and *fenofibrate*. Quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ yield of compound **3d** was found to be 58% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (158 mg, 0.331 mmol). The title product was obtained as a colourless oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 5:1 hexane:Et₂O).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{H} 7.42 – 7.37 (2H, m), 7.34 – 7.30 (5H, m), 7.29 – 7.25 (4H, m), 6.85 – 6.80 (2H, m), 5.07 (1H, hept, $J = 6.3$ Hz), 2.79 (1H, s), 1.59 (6H, s), 1.52 (2H, d, $J = 1.1$ Hz), 1.21 (6H, d, $J = 6.3$ Hz)

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_{C} 173.7, 155.4, 143.1, 137.8, 133.6, 130.3, 128.8, 128.6, 128.6, 128.5, 128.3, 127.7, 118.9, 117.1, 111.5, 79.3, 77.6, 69.1, 25.5, 25.5, 21.7, 9.7

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3481, 2981, 2871, 1726, 1605, 1488, 1288, 1100, 821, 760

HRMS (ESI+) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for C₂₉H₂₈³⁵ClNa₂O₄ 521.1466; Found 521.1469

(8*S*,9*S*,10*R*,13*R*,14*S*,17*R*)-10,13-Dimethyl-17-((*R*)-6-methylheptan-2-yl)-3-(2-phenylcycloprop-1-en-1-yl)-4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-3*H*-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3-ol, **3e**

Prepared following GP2 using (1,2,2-tribromocyclopropyl)benzene **1a** and 4-cholesten-3-one. Quantitative ¹H-NMR yield of compound **3b** was found to be 46% using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard (69 mg, 0.266 mmol, d.r. 1:1). The title product was obtained as a mixture of diastereoisomers (d.r. 30:70), affording a yellow oil after flash column chromatography on silica gel (hexane to 10:1 hexane:Et₂O).

Data reported for mixture of diastereoisomers

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.63 – 7.59 (1H, m, *major + minor*), 7.41 – 7.36 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 7.35 – 7.30 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 2.35 – 2.22 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 2.18 – 2.08 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 2.01 – 1.90 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 1.89 – 1.77 (m, 3H, *major + minor*), 1.73 – 1.67 (2H, m, *major + minor*), 1.60 – 1.46 (6H, m, *major + minor*), 1.42 – 1.26 (10H, m, *major + minor*), 1.18 – 1.05 (10H, m, *major + minor*), 0.92 – 0.83 (7H, m, *major + minor*), 0.68 (3H, s)

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 148.0, 130.1, 129.5, 128.7, 128.6, 128.3, 127.2, 123.5, 120.4, 120.0, 117.1, 110.1, 70.7, 56.4, 56.3, 54.2, 52.7, 42.7, 42.6, 40.1, 40.0, 39.7, 37.6, 37.3, 36.3, 36.2, 36.1, 35.9, 35.2, 33.1, 33.1, 32.8, 32.5, 32.4, 31.7, 30.6, 28.4, 28.2, 24.4, 24.0, 23.0, 22.7, 21.2, 19.7, 18.8, 18.8, 14.3, 12.2, 7.4

Note: signals are doubled due to the presence of diastereoisomers

IR (neat, ν cm⁻¹): 3421, 2931, 2866, 1597, 1676, 1374, 1019, 908, 759

HRMS (ESI+) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₃₆H₅₂ONa 523.3910; Found 523.3915

NMR spectra

1b

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

1c

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

-70.01

A (s)
-70.01

¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

¹³C{¹H} NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

21

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
(CDCl_3 , 101 MHz)

2r

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

2r

¹³C{¹H} NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

2s

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

2t

¹H NMR
(CDCl₃, 400MHz)

2t

¹³C{¹H} NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

2u

¹³C{¹H} NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

2y

¹³C{¹H} NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

Crystallographic Characterization

The crystals were obtained by slow evaporation of an hexane/Et₂O solution (95:5). X-ray data were acquired at room temperature with a Bruker AXS X8 APEXII automated diffractometer, equipped with a CCD detector and graphite-monochromatized Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) operating at 50 kV, 30 mA and 40 mm crystal-to-detector distance. Relevant crystallographic data of the investigated crystal is reported in **Table S1**. The whole Ewald sphere ($\pm h, \pm k, \pm l$) was recorded up to $\theta \sim 25^\circ$ with a scan width $0.8^\circ/\text{frame}$ and an exposure time $120 \text{ s}/\text{frame}$. The APEX program suite allowed to optimize the collection strategy; [8] the SAINT package [9] was used for the integration of the intensities of reflections and the correction of the Lorentz and polarization effects; the SADABS software [10] was employed for the empirical absorption correction; XPREP [11] was used for the subsequent analysis of the intensity data and the assignment of the space group. Structure was solved by charge flipping method [12] and refined in $P2_1/c$ space group by full-matrix least-square analysis using the program CRYSTALS. [13] All reflections are included in the refinement. Overall scale factor, atomic positions and anisotropic atomic displacement parameters of non-hydrogen atoms were refined. All hydrogen atoms were located and refined isotropically through riding restraints conditions. [14]

Table S1 X-ray crystal data of

Chemical formula	C ₃₆ H ₃₂ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S
M_r	627.73
Crystal size (mm)	0.50 × 0.50 × 0.10
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, $P2_1/c$
Temperature (K)	293
a, b, c (Å)	11.6912 (6), 14.6013 (7), 18.9559 (9)
β (°)	90.392 (2)
V (Å ³)	3235.8 (3)
Z	4
R_{int}	0.062
No. of reflections, No. of parameters	4624, 406
$RI [F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)], wR(F^2), S$	0.053, 0.127, 0.98
$\Delta\rho_{\text{max}}, \Delta\rho_{\text{min}}$ (e Å ⁻³)	0.62, -0.62

Figure S1. ORTEP drawing of compound **3c**. The displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level. Hydrogen atoms labels are omitted for clarity.

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